

**UNDERSTANDING THE CAUSATIVE FACTORS (NIDANA) OF AMLAPITTA IN THE
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ABSTRACT

Hyper acidity or *Amlapitta* is one of the most prevalent health issues today, primarily owing to improper eating and lifestyle choices. It is also one of many ailments of *Annavaha Srotas* caused by disturbed *Agni*. The cause of *Amlapitta* is excessive *Amla Guna* of *Pachaka Pitta* which occurs due to the accumulation of *Ama*. According to Ayurveda, the majority of diseases stem from a disturbance in *Agni*. Factors such as eating too much junk food, fast food, work stress, anxiety and other lifestyle habits have greatly influenced the increasing incidence of Hyperacidity. *Nidanas* of *Amlapitta* are different type which includes *Aharaja*, *Viharaja*, *Manasika* and *Agantuja*. *Pitta Dosh* is the most important *Dosha* responsible for *Amlapitta*, specifically due to the aggravation and the sourness of the *Pitta Dosh*. The *Amla Rasa* and *Amla Vipaka* therefore play a large role in the development of *Amlapitta*. The cause of *Amlapitta* is determined by the interplay of the *Doshas*, *Agni*, *Ama* and *Srotas*. This article emphasizes *Nidana* of *Amlapitta* in the Light of *Agni Dushti*.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda*, *Amlapitta*, *Agni Dushti*, *Hyper acidity*, *Nidana*.**INTRODUCTION**

Ayurveda described several illnesses related to the *Annavaha Srotas* or impaired digestion and *Amlapitta* is one of them which mainly arise due to the *Mithya Ahara-Vihara*. The majority of Ayurvedic classical treatises refer to *Amlapitta* which can be correlated to hyperacidity as per the modern concept. The use of anti-inflammatory medications, steroids, in conjunction with an unhealthy lifestyle, increases the severity of this condition. The *Aharaja*, *Viharaja*, *Manasika* and *Agantuja Nidana* lead to poor digestion and consequently causes malfunction of the *Annavaha Srotas* which further produces pathogenesis of *Amlapitta*.^[1,4]

NIDANA

Improper dietary habits are the foremost cause of

Amlapitta, the intake of incompatible, excessively spicy, stale, sour and spoiled foods weakens the *Agni*, leading to *Agnimandya*. Increased consumption of *Amla* and *Vidahi* substances aggravates *Pitta*, and faulty eating practices further disturb digestion, ultimately resulting in *Amlapitta*. Psychological factors also play a significant role, as mental stress, worry, anxiety, fear, anger, and emotional disturbances adversely affect *Agni* and impair the digestive process. In addition, *Amlapitta* may develop due to external or iatrogenic causes such as the excessive or improper use of medications, irrational administration of *Ushna-Tikshna* drugs without proper consideration of individual constitution and dietary regulations, alcohol abuse, and indiscriminate drug consumption. Various *Nidana* of *Amlapitta* are also depicted in **Table 1**.^[4,7]

Table 1: Causative Factors (*Nidana*) of *Amlapitta*.

Category	Type of Hetu	Causative Factors
1	<i>Aharaja Hetu</i>	<i>Viruddha Ahara</i> and <i>Dushta Ahara</i> leads to <i>Agnimandya</i> , while excessive <i>Amla</i> and <i>Vidahi</i> foods aggravate <i>Pitta</i> .

		<i>Atiushna, Atisheeta, Atisnigdha, Atiruksha, Atiguru, Atidrava, Atighana, Atiamla, Abhishyandi and Viruddha Ahara.</i>
		<i>Abhojana, Atibhojana and Adhyashana.</i>
2	<i>Viharaja Hetu</i>	Unhealthy lifestyle practices disturb <i>Agni</i> and aggravate <i>Pitta</i> . Day sleep after meals, suppression of natural urges, irregular sleep, improper meal timings and eating during indigestion.
Category	Type of Hetu	Causative Factors
3	<i>Manasika Hetu</i>	Anxiety and fear vitiate <i>Agni</i> , causing irregular digestion and leading to <i>Amlapitta</i> .
4	<i>Agantuja Hetu</i>	Excessive or improper use of medications, irrational administration of <i>Ushna-Tikshna</i> drugs without considering <i>Prakriti</i> .

Rupa of Amlapitta

Avipaka, Utklesha, Aruchi and *Tikta-Amla Udgara* are among the *Samanya Lakshana* of *Amlapitta*. Patients frequently report *Guru Koshta* and *Hridaya-Kantha Daha*. *Acharya Kashyapa* has also mentioned symptoms like *Hridshula, Vidbheda, Udara Adhmana* and *Antrakujana*. Additional symptoms that may indicate systemic involvement in *Amlapitta* include *Shiroruja, Klama, Romaharsha* and *Gaurava*. A poor diet and lifestyle are closely associated with all of the causes of

Amlapitta. *Agni* is disturbed and *Pitta* is vitiated by improper eating habits, irregular meal schedules and mental stress, etc. eventually result in *Amlapitta*.^[5,7]

TYPES OF AMLAPITTA

Amlapitta is classified based on *Dosha Dushti* and *Sthana Dushti*. *Amlapitta* is composed of three types of vitiated *Doshas*; *Vataja, Pittaja* and *Kaphaja*; whereas another reference describes four different *Amlapitta* varieties as depicted in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Various types of *Amlapitta*.

In addition to the aforementioned classification based on vitiated *Doshas*, the condition can also be classified on the basis of *Sthana Dushti*. Based on *Sthana Dushti* classification, *Amlapitta* can be classified into *Urdhwaga Amlapitta* and *Adhoga Amlapitta*. *Urdhwaga Amlapitta* occurs when the vitiated *Doshas* move upward and produce symptoms of sour belching, nausea, and/or burning in the stomach; whereas *Adhoga Amlapitta* occurs when the vitiated *Doshas* move downward and produce loose stools and/or a burning sensation in lower part of gastrointestinal tract.^[6,8]

Samprapti

The primary *Samprapti Ghatakas* of *Amlapitta* are the *Doshas* of *Pachaka Pitta, Samana Vayu* and *Kledaka Kapha*; the *Dushya* is *Rasa Dhatu*; and the *Agni* affected by *Amlapitta* is *Jatharagni*. This *Jatharagni* produces *Jatharagnijanya Ama* and affects *Annavaha* and *Rasavaha Srotas* with *Srotodushti* due to either *Sanga* or *Vimarga Gamana*. The *Udbhava Sthana, Adhishthana*, and *Vyakta Sthana* of *Amlapitta* are *Amashaya*. The *Sanchara Sthana* of *Amlapitta* is *Mahasrotas*. *Amlapitta* is classified under the *Abhyantara Roga Marga* and is a *Sadhya Vyadhi* condition when managed appropriately.^[7,9]

Management of Amlapitta

In treating *Amlapitta*, the most important aspect of treatment is *Ahara Chikitsa* because the main cause of *Amlapitta* is due to dietary factors. Ayurveda addresses *Amlapitta* by correcting *Agnimandya* and eliminating *Ama* from the body first before using additional means of treatment. Therapies that purify the body through *Shodhana* include *Mridu Virechana, Mridu Vamana, Niruha Basti* and *Anuvasana Basti*. The method of purification used on the patient should be based on his/her level of strength and health, since only gentle purification procedures will be used on those who are weak, while more aggressive purification procedures may be used on stronger individuals.

Certain *Shamana* therapies may be done using *Langhana* and receiving *Tikta Rasa* predominant *Pachana* drugs. Some examples of *Tikta Rasa* are predominant *Pachana* drugs include *Triphala, Patola, Neem, Giloy, Haritaki* and *Shatavari*.

Management of *Amlapitta* also requires changes to the patient's diet and lifestyle. Patients should eat several smaller and more frequent meals, preferably during *Pitta Kala* or at times of true hunger. Patients should chew

their food thoroughly, drink enough water prior to eating, and be in a calm and relaxed mental state while they eat their food. Foods that should be avoided by patients with *Amlapitta* are extremely hot or cold foods, alcohol and junk food. Foods that are beneficial for patients with *Amlapitta* include old rice, barley, cucumber, wheat, cow's milk and bitter gourd.^[8,10]

CONCLUSION

Amlapitta is a prevalent and serious condition that has arisen due to changes in lifestyle and unhealthy eating habits. *Amlapitta* is caused by the interaction of factors such as; *Ahara*, *Vihara* and *Manasika Nidana*. These factors play an important role in the pathophysiology of *Amlapitta*. The development of *Amlapitta* is due to the *Prapoka* and *Vidagha* of *Pitta*. In order to successfully treat *Amlapitta*, it is necessary to pacify the aggravated *Pitta* utilizing therapeutic agents that are either sweet in nature or have cold properties. Strict compliance with *Pathya* and *Nidana parivartan* are essential for effective management of *Amlapitta*.

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